

CLICK, SWIPE, LEARN: DUOLINGO'S IMPACT ON ENGLISH LEARNING AMONG PAKISTANI UNDERGRADUATES

Azka Jabbar¹, Dr. Naveed Nawaz Ahmad², Dr. Rabia Faiz^{*3}, Dr. Hafiz Ahmad Bilal⁴

¹MPhil English (Linguistics), Department of English Language and Linguistics, University of Sargodha

²Assistant Professor, Department of English Language and Linguistics, University of Sargodha

^{*3}Assistant Professor, Department of English, University of Sargodha

⁴Professor of English, Higher Education Department, Punjab

¹azkajabbar789@gmail.com, ²naveed.nawaz@uos.edu.pk, ^{*3}rabia.faiz@uos.edu.pk,

⁴ahmadbilal.uos@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Rabia Faiz

Abstract

The study investigated the role of Duolingo in English language learning at the undergraduate level. The study focuses on the Pakistani context as English is the second language there. Duolingo is a language learning platform that is famous among second language learners at the undergraduate level. A mixed-method approach was used for analysis. A self-compiled questionnaire was built in order to find the frequency of the use of Duolingo among students, to see the benefits of Duolingo for English language learning compared to the language lab, and the rapidity of the use of technology by students. The data was collected using an Online Google form and the data was analyzed using SPSS, getting the results in the form of frequencies and percentages. The data is then interpreted using a qualitative approach. The findings show that students like to use Duolingo for learning the English language in Pakistan. There was a positive response from students to using novel technology or a mobile-based app for learning the English language at the undergraduate level. It is helpful for the students to learn the language in a fun way using Duolingo. It increases the efficiency and effectiveness of the students to learn the English Language. Duolingo is the recommended app for learning English language vocabulary at the undergraduate level.

INTRODUCTION

Language and technology are interrelated in terms of language learning. With the advancement of technology, AI has rapidly come into existence and become famous among the public. In the year 2025, it is impossible to consider that students are not exposed to AI or the novel apps. From reading to writing, listening to speaking, every skill can be improved by using AI or advanced apps. Duolingo is one of them. Duolingo is an app that is widely used by people to learn a language. It is a language learning app where students can learn many languages in a gamified and fun way. Duolingo provides an ecosystem where the student learns the language according to their own understanding level. There are around 1.2 billion people who want to learn a new language. Some are learning for fun,

and some are learning to get an opportunity. But learning a new language is very expensive and inaccessible to most people (Paqui Gualán, & Vivanco Loaiza, 2025). Duolingo is the app that is accessible to everyone, whether the person is a Hollywood star, a rich man or a budget-friendly student; everyone can access the expensive languages easily by using Duolingo. It uses implicit learning for the learner to teach new language, but it does not mean that it is only using implicit learning; it is also an important tool to teach explicit concepts. Over 500 million users are using Duolingo for learning languages. It is not easy to maintain the lessons for every user according to their difficulty level. So, Duolingo overcame it by using a machine learning algorithm. Learning

online is not easy, and it is boring. To motivate their learning, there are fun games and avatars with motivating quotes. In between their lesson, they take short exercises so that everyone stays consistent. Moreover, Duolingo sends notifications and has a streak game to maintain consistency (Ta'amneh et al., 2024). Duolingo has interactive stories and broadcasts in the lesson plan as an assessment to improve the language skills of the learners for real-life use. It helps their learner with interaction, communication, reading and listening comprehension skills for the English language. The English language is one of the prestige languages all over the world. It is an international language and is used globally to talk across nations. So the importance of learning English is high. It is the language used in institutions and academic writings. It is a formal and standard language. It is the language of the media. Everyone is attracted to the English language. Due to its importance, the demand for learning English is increasing day by day. In fact, many children have English as their first language (Aulia et al., 2020). In the Pakistani context, Urdu is a national language and English is learnt as a second language. The one who speaks English is considered educated and literate. English is considered the language of the elite class. So the interest to learn English is at its peak. People prefer to use English words in their conversation to gain respect in society. Undergraduate level students are most exposed to using technology, and they are mature enough to use AI tools; they know the importance of learning English very well. Duolingo is a tool that is suitable for learners of every age.

Significance of the Study:

The research is on the recent app, Duolingo, which helps students learn different languages. The app is particularly made for language learning. So, the study aims to find how quickly students adopt new technology and incorporate that into their routine for language learning. The study particularly focuses on English language learning, as it is a widely spoken language. English is an international language, and the use of English is increasing day by day. The students are motivated to learn the English Language to survive in the future world. The study focuses on Pakistani students, as for these students, English is a second language. In the Pakistani context, the people don't just learn the English Language for academic purposes but to achieve respect and social status as well. So, keeping the

importance of English in the Pakistani context, it is conducted in Pakistan. The study chooses students instead of local people, as students know the importance of the English language more than local people. Moreover, the study has targeted the learners as students to have exposure to the use of Duolingo in an academic setting. It aims to find the real use of Duolingo among undergraduate students. As the students at the undergraduate level are mature and critical. They know well how to use the new technologies. Most of them are Gen Z, who have seen the transformative phase of technology. They have developed cognition about the use of AI. The study aims to have a positive attitude towards the use of the English language learning by using Duolingo.

Research Objectives:

- To examine the use of Duolingo for the English language at the Undergraduate Level in Pakistan
- To find the efficiency of recent AI tools in English language learning
- To identify the adoptability of new technology for English language learning.

Research Questions:

- How frequently do Undergraduate Level students use Duolingo to learn the English Language?
- How quickly do the students adopt new technology for English language learning?
- How effective is the use of mobile mobile-based learning AI tool Duolingo for English language learning?

Literature Review:

The recent researches find Duolingo as a useful tool for learning vocabulary, particularly English language vocabulary. The studies show that learning the English language is not just restricted to classroom learning and academic settings, but it becomes a symbol of respect, status, and prestige in Pakistani society. The particular reason for the hype of the English language in Pakistan is British colonialism, as mentioned by Mehmood et al. (2024). The research focuses on the importance of English in socio-economic, cultural and educational systems of Pakistan. It highlights how English has evolved by discussing its history from British times to the present, in Pakistan, and also its impacts on the future. Moreover, this research highlights the

challenges and opportunities related to English proficiency in Pakistan. Irfan et al. (2024) investigated that all developing nations have an importance for the English language. The developing nation adopts the language for scientific and technological innovations. According to the research, it is difficult to teach English in Pakistan. There is a struggle by students to speak it well. The particular reason for this is how the English language is taught to the students. This study shows that even the teachers are facing issues in teaching English to the students. This problem is in the struggle phase, finding solutions to resolve this issue. Rehman (2020) focuses on the role of English language skills in developing students' identity. According to this research, English is not just a language but is necessary for developing students' personalities. The researchers worked with one hundred and fifty students belonging to different colleges in Lahore. All the skills of the English language, reading, writing, listening, and speaking, are necessary for communication, interacting with fellows, for social norms, and to present moral values, developing the overall personality of the students. It concluded that the educational institutions need to have frequent classes for the improvement of the grammar and vocabulary of the students. Aulia et al. (2020) focused on finding the effect of Duolingo for English vocabulary mastery on eighth-grade students. It was conducted in a junior high school, Jember. The results were analyzed using SPSS software, which gave the findings that 84.69 percent of students in experimental group has correct English vocabulary that used Duolingo and 80.78 percent students in controlled group has correct English vocabulary that had not used Duolingo for learning English language vocabulary. This shows that Duolingo is a good tool for increasing the vocabulary of students. Zainudin et al. (2025) conducted an experiment on tenth-grade students to master the English language vocabulary. The study concluded that there is a significant difference between those who used Duolingo and those who did not use it. Moreover, it says that Duolingo is an innovative and engaging tool to learn languages for the students. Ramdhani et al. (2025) found that the impact of Duolingo in the English course program, by keeping Gen Z as participants, there were thirty-nine elementary school students, aged seven to twelve. The experiment took five months to find the impact of mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) among

young learners in a non-formal education setting. The study contributed to a technology-based methodology that appreciated the gamified application to foster English language vocabulary and learners' motivation. Febriani et al. (2023) aim to find the problem that students have in understanding the vocabulary of verbs. The research was conducted on twelfth-grade students in the academic year of 2021 and 2022. The study concluded that Duolingo helps to improve present and past verb vocabulary. After using Duolingo, students were happily raising their hands in order to answer the 20 listed questions of vocabulary questions listed. They answered quickly in a correct manner. Sibuera (2025) researched 8/1 class students, who were the control group, and the experimental group was of 8/2 class. After conducting the result null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, that Duolingo is effective for English language vocabulary learners. Duolingo has gamified activities, fun-loving exercises, and user-friendly lessons. So, it helps the students to learn vocabulary, making it accessible and engaging. Nurhayati et al. (2024) assist in learning English vocabulary by using Duolingo. According to the research, Duolingo is the most popular tool for language learning. The research was conducted on EFL students to identify a bunch of difficulties in learning English vocabulary. The research concluded that there is a big improvement in the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group as compared to the control group. Intan et al. (2024) say that vocabulary mastery is important than grammar. Traditional learning includes rote learning. It is boring and depressing for the students, but Duolingo provides a modern solution to learn English vocabulary in a fun way. It has ranking and competition. There is a need to add mobile learning to contemporary education. Rouabhia et al. (2024) focus on instructing a second language context that uses Duolingo. It makes a comparison between Duolingo and a traditional methodology to see the impact of Duolingo on learners' motivation and engagement. It is concluded that Duolingo is a practical implementation application for classroom integration. In a nutshell, the research shows that English is an important medium of communication and it has its own importance in developing nations, such as in Pakistan. The demand for learning English vocabulary is increasing day by day. Among mobile-based learning tools, Duolingo is

one of the most popular tools for language learning. The research shows that Duolingo is an effective tool for all levels of students to learn English language vocabulary in a game form and fun manner.

Research Methodology:

A mixed method (both qualitative and quantitative methodologies) was used. Quantitative method was used to find out the data in the form of frequency and percentage, while the Qualitative method was used to interpret the results that were derived by using SPSS software. A convenient sampling technique was used to target the participants for the study.

Tool:

Self-constructed Questionnaire was used as a tool for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of twenty items, which were multiple-choice questions. Every question consisted of four options to identify the frequency of the use of Duolingo among English language learners, to find how rapidly students adopt new trends or apps for English language learning, and whether Duolingo is useful for them to learn English or not.

The Questionnaire was designed keeping the ethical considerations in mind. It consisted of two sections. The first section included the title of the research, a small description about the research, the consent portion, and the demographic information portion to be filled out. The second section consisted of the instructions to fill the questionnaire, a sample solved question to make things clearer, twenty items, a Thank-you note, and contact information of the researcher.

Participants:

The study consisted of 30 participants. The participants were of 16 to 25 years students, currently studying in 3rd, 4th and 5th semesters at the undergraduate level in the Department of English at the University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.

Data Collection:

The data was collected by using an Online Google form. The link of the Google form was sent to the class representatives and girls' representatives of 3rd, 4th and 5th semester students of the English Department, directly through WhatsApp. A well-structured text was sent, which included a few description about research in one to two lines, the link to the Google form and a thank-you note. The research got thirty responses within a week. The responses were extracted from the Google Form in an Excel sheet.

Data Analysis:

SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software was used to analyze the data in frequency and percentage form. The Excel file was uploaded to SPSS software, which converted the responses into statistical data in the form of percentages and frequencies. Those percentages were used to interpret the data.

Finding and discussion

The findings show that Duolingo is a mobile-based language learning AI tool that students at the undergraduate level in Pakistan use for learning the English language. It helps the students to learn all the skills of the English language, such as reading, writing, listening and speaking. It has amazing features and attractive themes.

How often do you use Duolingo to learn English?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Daily	17	58.6	58.6	62.1
Once a week	2	6.9	6.9	69.0
Rarely or never	8	27.6	27.6	96.6
Several times a week	1	3.4	3.4	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

The results show that 58.6 percent of the students use Duolingo daily for learning English language vocabulary. This shows how famous this app is among students and how attractive the features are, which grab the attention of students to use it daily.

How long have you been using Duolingo for English learning?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
1-3 months	1	3.4	3.4	6.9
3-6 months	2	6.9	6.9	13.8
Less than 1 month	22	75.9	75.9	89.7
More than 6 months	3	10.3	10.3	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

75.9 percent of the students have started to use this app in less than one month, which shows that this app has been adopted by the students in recent years.

Which English skill do you feel improves the most using Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Listening	2	6.9	6.9	10.3
Reading	6	20.7	20.7	31.0
Speaking	6	20.7	20.7	51.7
Vocabulary	14	48.3	48.3	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

Among English language learning skills, vocabulary learning is mostly improved by the students, which is 48.3 percent. Not just these other skills are also improving, but the percentage for speaking (20.7) and reading (20.7) is moderate. Similarly, the results of Aulia, H.R. et al.(2020) show that 84.69 percent of the students have improved their English language vocabulary after using Duolingo.

Which skill do you think improves the least while using Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Listening	7	24.1	24.1	27.6
Reading	5	17.2	17.2	44.8
Speaking	3	10.3	10.3	55.2
Writing	13	44.8	44.8	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

The findings show that writing skills (44.8) are the least improved skill among all, but it does not mean that it is totally ignored, as some of the least improved skills are listening (24.1), reading (17.2), and speaking (10.3).

How helpful is Duolingo for improving your English overall?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Moderately helpful	16	55.2	55.2	58.6
Not helpful at all	1	3.4	3.4	62.1
Slightly helpful	3	10.3	10.3	72.4
Very helpful	8	27.6	27.6	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

55.2 percent of the students choose that it is moderately helpful to use Duolingo for improving the English language overall and only 3.4 percent of students say that it is not helpful at all. So, there is a big difference between the two.

Do you feel more confident in using English after learning with Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Not confident	4	13.8	13.8	17.2
Slightly confident	9	31.0	31.0	48.3
Somewhat confident	5	17.2	17.2	65.5
Yes, very confident	10	34.5	34.5	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

It shows that 34.5 percent of students find it a useful app, which increased their confidence, 31 percent of students say that their confidence is slightly increased and 17.2 say they feel somewhat confident after using this app.

How motivated do you feel to learn English when using Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Highly motivated	7	24.1	24.1	27.6
Moderately motivated	11	37.9	37.9	65.5
Not motivated	5	17.2	17.2	82.8
Slightly motivated	5	17.2	17.2	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

The table shows that according to 37.9 percent of the students, they find themselves moderately motivated to learn English when using Duolingo. This also shows the eagerness of the students to learn the English language.

What mainly motivates you to use Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Easy accessibility	4	13.8	13.8	17.2
Free learning opportunities	13	44.8	44.8	62.1
Fun and gamified learning	5	17.2	17.2	79.3
Recommendations from others	6	20.7	20.7	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

Most of the students (44.8) like using this app because it is a free learning opportunity for them, 17.2 percent students use it because it is fun and gamified learning, as Intan et al. (2024), this tool provides a modern solution to learn vocabulary in a fun way.

Do you think Duolingo is better than traditional English learning methods?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
About the same	7	24.1	24.1	27.6
Much better	7	24.1	24.1	51.7
Slightly better	10	34.5	34.5	86.2

Worse	4	13.8	13.8	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

24.1 percent of students find it about the same to have traditional methods or Duolingo for English language learning. But the rest found it much better (24.1) and slightly better (34.5) and 13.8 found it a worse idea compared to the traditional English learning methods.

Is Duolingo more effective than language labs used in schools/colleges?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
About the same	6	20.7	20.7	24.1
Less effective	9	31.0	31.0	55.2
Slightly more effective	2	6.9	6.9	62.1
Yes, much more effective	11	37.9	37.9	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

For 37.9 percent of the students, it is much more effective than language labs, which shows that, due to its features, students like it more than

Should educational institutions include Duolingo as part of English learning?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Definitely yes	3	10.3	10.3	13.8
No	6	20.7	20.7	34.5
Not sure	9	31.0	31.0	65.5
Probably yes	10	34.5	34.5	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

Duolingo is best for a non-formal educational setting, according to the findings, only 10.3 percent of the students say that educational institutions include Duolingo as a part of English learning.

How easy is it for you to use Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Difficult	4	13.8	13.8	17.2
Easy	12	41.4	41.4	58.6
Very difficult	1	3.4	3.4	62.1
Very easy	11	37.9	37.9	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

Duolingo is a very easy and fun-loving app to use by the students. 41.4 percent of students find it easy to use.

Does Duolingo provide enough practice to improve your listening skills?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
A little	6	20.7	20.7	24.1
Somewhat	13	44.8	44.8	69.0
Yes, very much	9	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

Duolingo is also highly beneficial for the students to learn listening skills, as none of the students has chosen No, not at all option. All of them have chosen somewhat (44.8), yes, very much(31), a little (20.7)

How effective is Duolingo in developing your reading comprehension?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Moderately effective	8	27.6	27.6	31.0
Not effective	1	3.4	3.4	34.5
Slightly effective	10	34.5	34.5	69.0
Very effective	9	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

The finding shows that Duolingo is also useful for understanding the reading comprehension of the students.

Does Duolingo help you improve your English pronunciation?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Not at all	1	3.4	3.4	6.9
To some extent	6	20.7	20.7	27.6
Very little	8	27.6	27.6	55.2
Yes, significantly	13	44.8	44.8	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

The results show that Duolingo focuses on not just vocabulary, but it is also helpful in improving pronunciation and other skills.

Does Duolingo help you remember new English vocabulary?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Moderately	9	31.0	31.0	34.5
Not effectively	1	3.4	3.4	37.9
Slightly	5	17.2	17.2	55.2
Very effectively	13	44.8	44.8	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

For 44.8 percent of the students, Duolingo is very effective in remembering English vocabulary. Similarly, Zainudin S. et al.(2025) find Duolingo as an innovative and effective vocabulary tool for use in school.

How satisfied are you with your English progress after using Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Not satisfied	2	6.9	6.9	10.3
Satisfied	15	51.7	51.7	62.1
Slightly satisfied	7	24.1	24.1	86.2
Very satisfied	4	13.8	13.8	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

51.7 percent of students are satisfied with using Duolingo for English language learning progress, which shows that they really like that.

Do you feel that Duolingo makes English learning more enjoyable?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
Agree	9	31.0	31.0	34.5
Disagree	4	13.8	13.8	48.3
Strongly agree	13	44.8	44.8	93.1
Strongly disagree	2	6.9	6.9	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

44.8 percent of students strongly agree that the Duolingo app makes English learning more enjoyable, which means that the tool is made for the targeted audience of this era, according to their taste. As Gen Z is fun-loving and attracted to engaging tools. The same is the thing that Ramdhani et al. (2025) have discussed in their research that Duolingo, a mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) tool, helps to foster vocabulary mastery among Gen Z.

What is your main purpose for using Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
For fun and personal interest	10	34.5	34.5	37.9
To communicate better in daily life	5	17.2	17.2	55.2
To improve English for academic use	10	34.5	34.5	89.7
To prepare for exams	3	10.3	10.3	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

Every option gains the interest of the students in answering the purpose of using Duolingo. Most of the students use Duolingo for fun and personal interest (34.5), which shows that young generate feel free to use innovations and technology, and to improve English for academic use (34.5), which highlights the demand and need for learning the English language in Pakistan at the undergraduate level. 17.2 Present students use it to communicate better in their daily life.

Do you believe your English proficiency has improved since using Duolingo?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3.4	3.4	3.4
A little	4	13.8	13.8	17.2
Not at all	5	17.2	17.2	34.5
To some extent	6	20.7	20.7	55.2
Yes, a lot	13	44.8	44.8	100.0
Total	29	100.0	100.0	

44.8 students say that after using Duolingo, their proficiency is increasing a lot, 20.7 percent say to some extent, 13.8 percent say a little, which means that Duolingo is helping the students to get improvement in English proficiency. To sum up, the findings highlight that Duolingo is a popular app among students of undergraduate

level in Pakistan for learning the English language; it provides the students with a free platform to learn all the skills of English. It attracts Gen Z for its amazing features and attractive themes. It is highly recommended to use Duolingo for learning the English language.

Conclusion:

To sum up, the study aims to find how frequently undergraduate-level students use Duolingo in their lives for English language learning. The findings show that Duolingo is a platform that helps students learn the English language. Students really like novel apps and they love to try new things. It focuses on daily life conversation to help the students increase their speaking skills. The study targets the use of AI for learning the English language. With the advancement in technology, science, and AI, it is necessary to adopt the changes and stay up to date for language learning. The students, especially teenagers, adopt new trends very quickly. These changes and trends can be added to the education system or curriculum to enhance better learning outcomes. The study concluded that Duolingo is the best tool for English language learning so far for undergraduate-level students in the Pakistani context. However, the research has some limitations; future research can be on other tools as well.

Limitations of the study and Future Recommendations:

The study is limited to a small population. The population or the number of participants can be more than thirty. Moreover, it has taken the participants at the undergraduate level. The research can be conducted on the other level of students or English language learners, such as secondary, primary, or higher levels. By doing this, the participants can have different age groups, other than 16 to 25. It has just focused on the English language. Duolingo is a tool that learners use to learn multiple languages, not just the English language. So, the future research can be on a different language, other than the English language. The study is conducted in Sargodha, a Pakistani context. Duolingo is a widely used app, all over the world, not just in Pakistan. Future research can be on other areas of the world to see the use of Duolingo in their specific area. The study does not explore the other AI tools that are used for language learning, such as YouTube videos, Instagram reels, ChatGPT or platforms like free 4 talk to learn languages. It aims at language learning, not language teaching. Duolingo helps teachers to devise new ideas or techniques for teaching the English language. The future research can be on the use of modern technology or AI tools in English language teaching.

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Appendix:

Online Google Form Questionnaire:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSenOHbB-iv0i_JLEt14PezS4jnS4nOMi5iQUKr2ubbQn6MzA/viewform?usp=publish-editor

